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Cybersecurity Threats: State of Bangladeshi Cybersecurity Laws and Institutions

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Abstract

In the present world, the concept of cybersecurity is as important as the physical security of a person, wealth and institution. Because of the growing interconnection of individuals through information and communication technology, the world is facing a major paradigm shift in regard to cyberspace technologies. Also, the criminals are changing their techniques fast, and the technologies to prevent crimes are rapidly becoming outdated and so are becoming the various legal and institutional arrangements to prevent such crimes. As part of the modern world, Bangladesh is bound to adapt to such a fast change of the technologies and to adjust its legal and institutional settings according to the need of the time. This study is an approach to analyze the various legal and institutional aspects of cybersecurity, the importance of cybersecurity laws and the various socio-economic and political impacts of such laws including an attempt to analyze the various negative impacts and an endeavor to suggest solutions to those problems.

1. Introduction:

The idea of another world beyond our visibility has been developed throughout the time as we became more interconnected through the internet. This is called the cyber world or cyberspace. Like the real space around us, the cyberspace is expanding at the same pace as that of the world's new population embracing the blessings of modern information and communication technologies for their day to day personal communication and convenience. Being part of the modern world, Bangladesh cannot ignore the various constantly changing challenges of cyberspace and must ensure necessary legal and institutional arrangements for the safeguard of its own cyberspace. But there are multi-dimensional problems in the Bangladeshi legal system and institutional arrangement that might threaten the safety of cyberspace and various exploitations of such problems could be possible to gain the immoral means of evil persons within and outside of the political boundary of Bangladesh.

2. The Concepts Defined:

The matter of security comes into question whenever there is a threat of criminal activities. That's why it is necessary to understand what it means by cybercrime first. Cybercrime means computer-oriented crime which involves a computer and a network.¹ In 1982, the term cybercrime was first introduced by William Gibson and later on it was popularized in

¹ Moore, Robert, 'Cybercrime: Investigating High-Technology Computer Crime', Second Edition, Anderson Publishing, 2005, p. 4.

his novel *Neuromancer*, which referred to "the mentally constructed virtual environment within which networked computer activity takes place."²

According to Solms & Niekerk, "cybersecurity is the collection of tools, policies, security concepts, security safeguards, guidelines, risk management approaches, actions, training, best practices, assurance and technologies by which cyber environment, organization and user's assets can be protected."³ Various aspects related to cyberspace security are yet unclear and are developing day by day through the constant contribution of the scholars. In the Bangladeshi law related to cyber security, the words "digital security"⁴ was used instead of "cyberspace security". In the definition clause of the act, the term digital security is defined as the security of any digital device or digital system.⁵ Though in a narrow sense, such term does not clearly identify the concept of cyber security as cyberspace includes more than just the security of digital devices and systems; rather it was intended to ensure the security of the persons using those devices and systems and also include all the other non-digital components that could have been included in doing so. Yet, it is not a major problem enforcing the law as other components of the law in combine works for the function of cyberspace security.

3. Necessity of Cyber Security:

From the late 20th century, with an increasing access to information communication technologies, people around the world became dependent on cyberspace. People became more connected using such technologies and later on we see that such technologies were replacing the stereotype components of life. Especially with the availability of cell phones and now with the availability of smart phones, the life of the modern human has changed radically. Even the poor people of third-world countries now have access to smartphones and mobile internet. Business, offices, government institutions are now very much focused on their activities in the cyberspace. Not only are they active in their own websites but also there is a strong social media presence of these institutions. Therefore, a need was felt to enact laws that will regulate the behavior of persons and institutions participating in such environments. And as a result, various laws were enacted in the legal systems around the world.

Feeling the necessity of such a new law, Bangladesh enacted the Information and Communication Technology Act, 2006. For over a decade, that law was the key legal source of cyber security provisions in Bangladesh. But as the national and international context changed radically, a need was felt to enact an updated law. The government of Bangladesh enacted the Digital Security Act, 2018 to meet such needs of the time.

4. Challenges Regarding Cyber Security:

² David Wall, *Cybercrime: The Transformation of Crime in the Information Age*, 1st edition, Polity 2007 10.

³ ITU, 'Definition of cyber security' (ITU, 2020) available at:

<https://www.itu.int/en/ITU->

[T/studygroups/com17/Pages/cybersecurity.aspx#:~:text=Cybersecurity%20is%20the%20collection%20of.and%20organization%20and%20user's%20assets](https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-) > last accessed 13 September 2020

⁴ Digital Security Act 2018, section 1.

⁵ *ibid* section 2(f)

One of the main problems of ensuring the rule of law in cyberspace is the matter of jurisdiction. Modern information and communication technologies have developed very fast over time, and the interconnections of the people around the world have increased radically and also increasing every moment, so do the risks connected to online communication have become increasingly pressing. As such communication are not separated by any physical boundary and are global in nature, the current international legal structure and concept of sovereignty is facing a challenge. And such unlimited existence of cyberspace makes it a sanctuary for the criminals. As a result, we see cyber-attacks on states and individuals. A recent example of such an attack is the ATM fraud committed in Bangladesh by foreign hackers.⁶ Also, the Bangladesh Bank hacking incident was a major cybercrime activity that shaken not only Bangladesh but also the whole world.⁷ It showed us how vulnerable Bangladeshi cyber security is. Also, it identified that our officials weren't ready to handle such international incidents as we see there was a long delay in filing the case in this matter.

5. The Multi-Level Risks:

The blessings and risks associated with cyber technology have now become part of modern human life. Crimes have turned into cybercrime which is facilitated by the network and computer technologies. War has turned into a cyber-war. Terrorism became cyber terrorism. So, it is a pressing need of today's world that law accommodates these concepts.⁸ Risks of cyberspace have manifested on a national, transnational and international level. Therefore, cyberspace threat is a multi-level threat and it requires multi-level approaches to secure it. As information technologies became increasingly prevalent, it became clear that the global society finds itself in the midst of a technological paradigm shift.⁹ The unprecedented capacity of information technology devices has enabled us global access to one-to-many and many-to-many communication which is never seen before.¹⁰

With billions of people relying on the internet for a wide variety of economic, social, and political interactions, cyberspace “is nothing short of essential to modern life.”¹¹ It is estimated that by the end of the year 2020, the number of networked devices will outnumber people by six to one, transforming current conceptions of communication and

⁶ Star Report, 'ATM Fraud Never Seen Before; 6 Foreigners Held', The Daily Star, June 3, 2019, available at: <<https://www.thedailystar.net/city/news/atm-fraud-never-seen-6-foreigners-held-1752871>> last accessed on 10 October 2020.

⁷ Raju Gopalakrishnan, Manuel Mogato, 'Bangladesh Bank Official's Computer Was Hacked To Carry Out \$81 million heist: diplomat', U.S., 2016, available at: <<https://www.reuters.com/article/us-cyber-heist-philippines/bangladesh-bank-officials-computer-was-hacked-to-carry-out-81-million-heist-diplomat-idUSKCN0YA0CH>> last accessed 8 July 2019.

⁸ Artur Appazov, 'Legal Aspects of Cyber security' Justits Ministeriet, 2014, available at: <https://www.justitsministeriet.dk/sites/default/files/media/Arbejdsomraader/Forskning/Forskningspuljen/Legal_Aspects_of_Cybersecurity.pdf> last accessed on 13 September 2020

⁹ *Ibid*

¹⁰ Julie Mehan, 'Cybercrime: The Transformation of Crime in tCyberwar, Cyberterror, Cybercrime: A Guide to the Role of Standards in an Environment of Change and Danger', 1st edition, IT Governance Ltd 2008, 9

¹¹ Melanie Teplinsky, 'Fiddling on the Roof: Recent Developments in Cyber security', 2013, 2(2) American University Business Law Review, 227-228

social interaction.¹² But the internet was never intended to be used by so many people and for the vast number of functions it performs today. Rather it was designed to enable a small group of scientists to share unclassified reports. So, initially, it was not designed to securely transfer sensitive data.¹³

Furthermore, the initial design of the internet does not allow easy monitoring of individual user behavior. Also, it was not designed to protect against attacks originating from within the internet itself.¹⁴ Unfortunately, that same old design persists even today, mostly unchanged, while the internet's uses have evolved drastically.¹⁵ The frequency of cyber-attacks and their sophistication is likely to increase day by day because instructions for sophisticated attack methods are getting more widely available via the internet which reduces the technical knowledge that is required to carry out a cyber-attack.¹⁶ The participants of cyber-attacks include criminal enterprises, cause-based groups, proxies for governments, and governments (including their military and intelligence agencies).¹⁷ The motives for the attacks range from financial gain to the advancement of national security interests, for peer recognition, and for the satisfaction of various other causes.¹⁸ Interestingly, the academic discourse on the social impact of new technology is nothing new. It was a longstanding concern expressed in the volumes on industrial sociology from Karl Marx to many contemporary commentators.¹⁹

6. Challenges Regarding Mitigation of Risks:

One of the major challenges is the jurisdictional fragmentation.²⁰ The main point of jurisdictional fragmentation is that the traditional concept of jurisdiction does not and cannot agree with the global nature of cyberspace.²¹ Jurisdiction is linked to the notion of state sovereignty which imposes an area of the exclusive responsibility of a sovereign state

¹² 'UN, *Comprehensive Study on Cybercrime*', United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, February 2013, available at: <https://www.unodc.org/documents/organized-crime/UNODC_CCPCJ_EG.4_2013/CYBERCRIME_STUDY_210213.pdf> last accessed on 10 October 2020

¹³ Howard Lipson, *Tracking and Tracing Cyber-Attacks: Technical Challenges and Global Policy Issues*, Carnegie Mellon University, November 2002, available at: <https://resources.sei.cmu.edu/asset_files/SpecialReport/2002_003_001_13928.pdf> last accessed 10 October 2020

¹⁴ *Supra Note 8*

¹⁵ *Ibid.*

¹⁶ William Stahl, *The Uncharted Waters of Cyberspace: Applying the Principles of International Maritime Law to the Problem of Cyber security*, 2011, 40(1) Georgia Journal of International and Comparative Law 248.

¹⁷ *Supra Note 8*

¹⁸ David Satola, *Towards a Dynamic Approach to Enhancing International Cooperation and Collaboration in Cyber security Legal Frameworks: Reflections on the Proceedings of the Workshop on Cyber security Legal Issues at the 2010 United Nations Internet Governance Forum*, Mitchell Hamline School of Law, 2011, available at: <<https://open.mitchellhamline.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1427&context=wmlr>> accessed 10 October 2020

¹⁹ David Wall, *Cybercrime: The Transformation of Crime in the Information Age*, 1st edition, Polity 2007, 10.

²⁰ *Supra Note 8*

²¹ *Ibid.*

over its territory and its citizens, excluding any extra-jurisdictional involvement of other states.²² But no state can claim sovereignty over cyberspace and introduce effective state regulations to govern it.²³ Interestingly, places like the European Union have solved the problem regarding jurisdiction by making their laws correspond to each other and by coherently regulating similar conduct but this is not the scenario of the whole world.²⁴ It is a matter of concern that many developing countries neither have the relevant laws that regulate conduct in cyberspace nor do they have the capacity to enforce cyber security laws.²⁵

Moreover, it is a matter of concern that it is almost impossible on the internet to distinguishing between participants standing behind an attack: whether it was by an individual or a government.²⁶ Such a thing happened in the case of the Bangladesh Bank cyber-attack where it was claimed that the state of North Korea was involved.²⁷ Though Bangladesh had the legal arrangement to prosecute such crimes that occurred outside of its territory,²⁸ it was impossible to identify and prosecute such culprits as the Bangladeshi legal system does not have the practical capacity to prosecute such persons or institutions. So, it is clear that various national and international laws are needed which can ensure justice for the victims, whether states, companies or individuals, in cases like the one of Bangladesh. Therefore, we will now evaluate the effectiveness of the existing Bangladeshi law to ensure justice in such cases.

7. Cybersecurity Laws in the Bangladeshi Context:

At present, there are legal provisions in Bangladesh to safeguard individuals and various state institutions from the threat of cybercrime. The principle law regarding cyber security in the country is the 'Digital Security Act, 2018' which is being applied along with the 'Information and Communication Technology Act, 2006'²⁹ and the various court decisions. The Digital Security Act mainly deals with the security issues related to the digital system. There are provisions regarding the creation of a Digital Security Agency, the jurisdiction of such agency, provisions regarding creating a Digital Security Council and the power of such council, specified crimes and their punishments, etc. in the Digital Security act, 2018. On the other hand, the Information Communication Technology Act, 2006 deals with the basic legal provisions regarding information communication technologies or cyberspace equipment.

²² UN, '*Comprehensive Study on Cybercrime*', United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, February 2013, available at: <https://www.unodc.org/documents/organized-crime/UNODC_CCPCJ_EG.4_2013/CYBERCRIME_STUDY_210213.pdf> last accessed 10 October 2020

²³ Michael Schmitt, '*Tallinn Manual on the International Law Applicable to Cyber Warfare*', 1st edition, Cambridge University Press 2013, 16

²⁴ *Supra Note 8*

²⁵ *Ibid.*

²⁶ *Ibid.*

²⁷ '*Bangladesh Bank Heist Was 'State-Sponsored'*: U.S. Official, CA, 2017, available at: <<https://ca.reuters.com/article/businessNews/idCAKBN1700TI-OCABS>> last accessed 7 July 2019.

²⁸ Information & Communication Technology Act 2006, section 4.

²⁹ Digital Security Act 2018, section 6.

The main problem with such a legal arrangement is it was made mainly for political purposes to make silent the opposing voice rather than solving the real problem. According to the concern expressed by the Sampadak Parishad, “The act gives unlimited power to the police to enter premises, search offices, bodily search persons, seize computers, computer networks, servers, and everything related to the digital platforms”.³⁰ According to the law, the police can arrest anybody on suspicion without a warrant and do not need any approval of any authorities.³¹ There are provisions regarding blocking data by the director-general of the digital security agency.³² But the grounds that justify such removal are too vaguely codified and can be used for the evil means of subduing the opposing voice and the freedom of electronic and print media. According to some critics, the arrest of the Bangladeshi photographer Shahidul Alam was such an evil act.³³

Moreover, the provision to preserve the spirit of the great Liberation War of 1971³⁴ through this law is not a bad provision but given the past experience of attempts at its distortion, such term should have been made clarified as 'spirit of Liberation War' is a rather vague term. There are further ambiguities regarding the concept of "attacking, false or intimidating information or data"³⁵ and these provisions may directly affect all investigative reporting in the media. Investigative reports are generally about the irregularities performed by institutions and individuals. There is a high risk that such corrupt people will use this law to intimidate journalists and media organizations and try to prevent publication of such stories. Any investigative report that reveals corruption about a person or an institution is bound to irritate, embarrass or humiliate someone and this notion was established by many landmarking court decisions.³⁶ Because of this provision publishing any negative report about any incident of corruption will be difficult as there might be more false cases against the reporter to harass them.

Also, the vague provisions regarding crimes and penalty for deterioration of law and order³⁷ may further hinder any reports or social media statements about the discrimination any race or ethnicity facing or the exploitation of any gender or race as such reports or statements might result in civil protest. Section 32 of the Digital Security Act³⁸ has the same elements as the repealed section 57 of the ICT Act, 2006, although it was a major demand by the various human rights groups and the concerned citizens of the country to abolish that provision.³⁹ Clearly, the Act has the potential to severely curtail freedom of the press and

³⁰ Sampadak Parishad, 'Why Sampadak Parishad opposes the Digital Security Act', The Daily Star, 01 October 2018, available at: <<https://www.thedailystar.net/frontpage/news/why-sampadak-parishad-opposes-the-digital-security-act-1640269>> last accessed on 13 September 2020

³¹ *Supra Note*, 29 section 43.

³² *ibid*, section 8.

³³ Billy Perrigo, 'What the Arrest of Photographer Shahidul Alam Means for Press Freedom in Bangladesh', TIME, 07 August 2018, available at: <<https://time.com/5359850/bangladesh-photographer-arrest-shahidul-alam-protests/>> last accessed on 13 September 2020.

³⁴ *Supra Note* 29, Section 21

³⁵ *ibid*, section 25.

³⁶ *New York Times Company v Sullivan* [1962] Supreme Court, 376 US (Supreme Court).

³⁷ *Supra Note* 29, Section 31

³⁸ *ibid*, section 32.

³⁹ 'Bangladesh: Protect Freedom of Expression' Human Rights Watch, 2018, available at: <<https://www.hrw.org/news/2018/05/09/bangladesh-protect-freedom-expression>> accessed 8 July 2019

expression to shrink people's freedom of thoughts and their right to express opinions on different mediums, including on digital platforms.

The act is a great threat for poets because poetic minds are not bound by law and most of the time; we see famous poets like our national poet Kazi Nazrul Islam are tended to think beyond the law. Also, the natural tendency of expressing an instant opinion regarding any incident on social media by the people is also abrogated through this law. The result might be a high rate of rumors than before as in a society where freedom of expression is being shrunk there are just whispers of misinformation. Most importantly, the problem regarding jurisdiction and the challenge regarding the state's sovereignty because of cyberspace has not been solved through the existing legal provisions. Also, no work has been done in regard to the proposed Digital Security Council.

Therefore, clearly the legal provisions in Bangladesh regarding cyber security bear the tension between the fundamental rights like freedom of expression, right to privacy, etc. and the imperative state law. Such tensions must be resolved.

8. Steps to Be Taken:

To identify the steps to resolve these problems, at first, we must acknowledge the fact that we are not asking for lawless cyberspace rather we are demanding cyberspace where there is rule of law. And also, when we are saying freedom of speech, we are actually acknowledging our fundamental right of freedom of thought and conscience and of speech subject to the reasonable restrictions imposed by law under article 39 of the Constitution of Bangladesh. So, the main question is whether various provisions of the Bangladeshi cyber security laws are unreasonably restricting our freedom of speech and thought and conscience or not. The answer we have found is, "Yes, they are." So, the parliament should clarify the vague provisions of sections 8, 21, 25, 28, 29, 31, 32, and 43 of the Digital Security Act, 2018. Meanwhile, the courts of Bangladesh should play an active role in upholding the fundamental rights of its citizens by interpreting and clarifying these vague provisions. A writ petition can be filled following the provisions of Article 102 to enforce the fundamental rights in respect of the Digital Security Act's mentioned provisions. The High Court Division should interpret the right to privacy generously and refuse to define the ambit of the right keeping in mind the Bangladeshi contextual realities.

A strong and updated cyberspace security policy is a must to encounter the future challenges of cyberspace security. Moreover, the government must take the necessary steps to build expert institutions to safeguard the Bangladeshi cyberspace. A cyber army can be built for that purpose. Also, steps must be taken to create the proposed Digital Security Council as soon as possible. Thus, the country may have a strong legal and institutional arrangement to face future threats of cybercrimes.

9. Conclusion:

Cyber security is a very sophisticated matter. No negligence can be done in its respect. Nowadays, Modern state systems are so much dependent on cyber communication that misuse of such a system can even lead to a large-scale nuclear warfare or other unimaginable disastrous situations. States can collapse because of their unsecured

cyberspace. Elections can be rigged and unworthy persons may become the leader of the nations through the misuse of cyberspace. Therefore, it is high time for Bangladesh to apprehend the importance of cyber security and to mitigate the above discussed legal and institutional problems regarding its cyberspace security otherwise, the nation may face devastating consequences.